

ASSESSMENT OF DRINKING WATER QUALITY IN EL-OBEID CITY-NORTH KORDOFAN STATE, SUDAN

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ABSTRACT

Background and Objective: Access to safe drinking-water is essential to health as water can become unsafe at any point between collection and consumption, this study aimed to assess the physicochemical and bacteriological quality of drinking water in El-Obeid City, North Kordofan State, Sudan (2022 – 2025). **Materials and Methods:** A descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted. Sample size determined according to World Health Organization (WHO) guidelines for water sampling measurement, the samples were distributed across three sources: households (20), animal carts (12), and pump/wells (8). water samples were collected and analyzed for parameters including (PH – Nitrite- Fluoride - Hardness – Calcium - Magnesium – Residual free chlorine and Total Dissolved Solids) and the presence of coliform bacteria *Escherichia coli* (*E.coli*). **Results:** The findings showed that 72.5% of water samples were contaminated with *Escherichia coli*, with the highest contamination from animal carts (83%), followed by households (70%), and pump/wells (62.5%). **Conclusion:** The findings emphasize the need for improved water treatment and targeted interventions to ensure safe drinking water and mitigate waterborne disease risks.

KEYWORDS: Water, Contamination, Quality, Membrane Filtration.

INTRODUCTION

Water is the basis of life and the central element of ecological balance.^[1] Access to safe drinking- water is essential to health, basic human right. The importance of water, sanitation, and hygiene for health and development has been reflected in the outcomes of a series of international policy forum.^[2] Much of the ill health that affects humanity, especially in developing countries, can be traced to a lack of safe and wholesome water supply.^[3] Recent studies in Africa and South America have shown that drinking water has been contaminated with *Escherichia coli*, *Enterococcus*, and various other bacteria. Fecal contamination of drinking water has been a major issue due to inadequate sanitation infrastructure.^[4] Housing area contaminate groundwater through improper storage and disposal of household wastes into landfills, dump sites, latrines and grave yards where they decay and are moved into aquifers by rainwater.^[5] Sanitation coverage has stagnated with more than 10.5 million people practice open defecation.^[6] in the rural areas of the developing countries the great majority of water quality problems are related to bacteriological contamination.^[7]

In Sudan, there are different sources for drinking water supply, surface water from rivers and streams (mainly the River Nile) rain water and ground water. Federal Ministry of Health reported in 2011 the microbiological contamination levels were found to be 10.3 % in Mogran water as to Buri 21.6% while in 2014, 15.3% contamination in Mogran and 44.7% in Buri.^[8,9] Even though water resources are available in Sudan, some parts of the country still continue to face significant water provision challenges.^[10] Microbiological contaminates such as viruses and bacteria, which may come from sewage treatment plants, septic systems, agricultural livestock operations and wildlife.^[11] To assess microbial water quality, verification typically relies on analyzing faecal indicator microorganisms, with *Escherichia coli* or *thermotolerant coliforms* as the preferred organisms. The presence of *Escherichia coli* indicates recent fecal contamination and is unacceptable in drinking water.^[12]

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Design

A descriptive cross-sectional study was carried out for assessment of the bacteriological quality of drinking water in El-Obeid City, North Kordofan State, Sudan (2022 – 2024).

Study Area

El-Obeid city, the capital of North Kordofan State in Sudan, is located between latitudes 11° and 13° North and longitudes 30° and 90° East, with an average altitude of 650 meters (approximately 2,133 feet) above sea level. It encompasses an area of approximately 81 square kilometers and lies about 588 kilometers (365 miles) southwest of Khartoum. **El-Obeid** sources its drinking water from two main origins; surface water and

groundwater. Surface water, located approximately 30 kilometers south of the city, includes three reservoirs and nine hafirs. Water from these sources is collected from heavy rains in hafirs across a large area and then transported to the water treatment plant in **El-Obeid** to prevent pollution, as well as undesirable taste and smell. Khor Bagara, situated in the Wad El-Baga area, is also located 30 kilometers south of El-Obeid, with water conveyed through three pipelines: two iron pipelines approximately 10 inches in diameter and another pipeline about 12 inches in diameter made of asbestos for the stations of Elaine, located 22 kilometers south, and Banoh, 11 kilometers south of El-Obeid. Currently, surface water in El-Obeid city is inaccessible. Groundwater is found in northern El-Obeid, which is almost 50 kilometers away, but it is not available for access at present.^[13]

Figure 1: The map of study site.

Source: <https://sd.maptons.com/2136649>

SAMPLING AND SAMPLE TECHNIQUES

Sample size

The sample size was selected according to (WHO) guidelines for water sampling measurement, which recommend taking one sample per 10,000 population, plus 10 additional samples.^[14] Whereas calculated the sample size base on the number of population (300681) in El-Obeid city was division on 10.000 of population plus 10 additional samples and was taken the total number of samples.

Number of population: 300681

300681 division on 10, 000 equals 30 and plus 10 additional samples equals 40.

Sample size: 30 samples + 10 additional samples.

Accordingly, a sample of 40 samples was obtained.

Sampling Techniques

This was done according to the standard methods for the examination of Water and waste water American Public Health Association (APHA) Standard Techniques, were followed.^[15] Methods analysis of samples by using laboratory protocols in ministry of water, all water samples were analyzed according to standard methods for water examination, and detection limit according to ministry of water.

Procedures

For purposes of study; El-Obeid City was divided into four equal quarters (clusters). The different types of blocks are considered as cluster where 10 samples were selected from each quarter of El-Obeid City using a method of simple random sampling. Drinking water samples were taken from houses, animal carts (Karo), and pump/wells. Sampling was conducted equally across all quarters, with (5) samples from houses, (3) samples from animal carts (Karo), and (2) samples from pump wells. Hence, the total number of samples selected is (40) from all blocks. The following tables show sample distribution:

Table (1): Distribution the sample size according to clusters, El-Obeid City.

Clusters	Numbers of sample
Eastern	10
Western	10
Northern	10
Southern	10
Total	40

After sample size determined from each clusters, samples acquired has distributed over blocks and a simple random

sample technique was used to select sample units. The following table shows the final sample size:

Table (2): Sample size acquired from different sources, El-Obeid City.

Source of samples	Number of samples
Houses	20
Animals carts	12
Wells/Pumps	8
Total	40

Instrumentation

Laboratory analysis was conducted using standard procedures, as illustrated the following.^[16]

- The samples were taken in 200 ml tubes analyzed for bacteriological (e.g., *E. coli*).
- Both Membrane Filtration (MF) technique and the multiple tube methods for water quality analysis was used to investigate the samples of water collected from the sources, transportation and storing vessels.
- Required; (Sterile filtration unit, sterile grid membrane filters, sterile 47 mm diameter cellulose pads, and sterile Petri dishes 50–60 mm diameter.

Steps in the membrane filter technique to *E. coli* examination

- Add an absorbent pad to a sterile Petri dish for the number of samples to be processed. A sterile pad was placed in the Petri dishes with sterile forceps.
- Soak the pad in nutrient medium, which is dispensed with a sterile pipette. A slight excess of medium (e.g., about 2.5 ml) should be added.
- Carefully remove a sterile membrane filter from the packet, holding it only by its edge.
- Place the membrane filter in the filtration apparatus, and clamp it in place
- Add sample to filtration apparatus.
- Apply the motor to the suction flask.
- Dismantle the filtration apparatus and remove the membrane filter using the sterile forceps, taking care to touch only the edge of the filter.
- Remove the lip of a previously prepared Petri dish and place the membrane grid side uppermost into the pad (agar). Lower the membrane, starting at one edge, in order to avoid trapping air bubbles.
- Label the Petri dish with the sample number. The sample volume should be also recorded.
- Put the Petri dish inside the incubate immediately, and the membrane is going to be incubated at 44 or 44.5 °C, the bacteria on it may first require time to acclimatise to the nature media.

10 After 24 hours of full incubation evidence result for *E. coli* per 100 ml of sample.

Confirmatory test for *E. coli* examination

For the examination of raw or partly treated waters, presumptive results may be adequate; however, in certain circumstances, it is important to perform conformity tests on pure subcultures. To confirm *E. coli* membranes, whether incubated at 35, 37, or 44°C, each colony (or a representative number of colonies) is subcultured into a tube of lactose peptone water and a tube of tryptone water. The tubes are incubated at 44°C for 24 hours. Confirmation of *E. coli* requires the addition of 0.2 - 0.3 ml of Kovacs reagent to each tryptone water culture. The production of a red colour indicates the synthesis of indole from tryptophan and confirms the presence of *E. coli*.

Statistical Analysis

After taking samples and tested, data were processed and analyzed by the computer software; Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS), Microsoft Excel and Master Sheet. It displayed or presented in tables and figures.

ETHICAL CONSIDERATION

To obtain permission to conduct the study is very important for data collection. The researcher will contact and receive approval from the appropriate management authority and will take.

RESULT

The study showed that about more than half (72.5%) of samples of drinking water from all sources were containing *faecal- E. coli*, (Figure 1). Whereas samples were taken from house, animals cart and wells/pump were contained *E. coli* in 100 - ml of samples; (70%), (83%) and (62.5%); respectively. (See Fig 2). Table (1): Reveals that the positive tests founding in eastern cluster; house (50%), animals cart (30%) and wells/pump (20%). Only (20%) of samples had contained *faecal E. coli* in western cluster. As contamination founding in northern cluster; house (80%),

animals cart (20%) and wells/pump (10%). In southern cluster the positive test discovered in house (10%),

animals cart (30%) and wells/pump (20%).

Figure (1): The distribution of faecal *E. coli* among drinking water samples in El-Obeid City. n=40

Figure (2): The distribution of faecal *E. coli* according to secondary sources, El-Obeid City.

Table (3): The distribution of total samples according to contaminated with faecal *E. coli* in different clusters, El-Obeid City.

Clusters/sources		House	Animals cart	Wells/Pump	Total			
Eastern clusters	Positive	5	50%	3	30%	2	20%	10/25%
	Negative	0	0%	2	20%	0	0%	2/5%
Western cluster	Positive	5	50%	1	10%	2	20%	8/20%
	Negative	4	80%	2	20%	1	10%	7/17.5%
Northern cluster	Positive	1	10%	1	10%	1	10%	3/7.5%
	Negative	5	50%	3	30%	2	20%	10/25%
Southern cluster	Positive	20	50%	12	30%	8	20%	40
Total								

Table (4): The Means statistics tested for compare differences across water sources of faecal *E. coli* and fluoride in drinking water samples, El-Obeid City.

F/SSMO* - F/WHO*		<i>E. coli</i> - House	<i>E. coli</i> - Wells/Pump	<i>E. coli</i> - Animals cart
Standard	N	-	1/2.5%	1/2.5%
	Mean	-	1.0000	1.0000
	Std. Deviation	-	0.0	0.0
Less than standard	N	19/47.5%	6/15%	7/17.5%
	Mean	1.3158	1.3333	1.1429
	Std. Deviation	0.47757	0.51640	0.37796
Above standard	N	1/2.5%	1/2.5%	4/10%
	Mean	1.0000	2.0000	1.2500
	Std. Deviation	0.0	0.0	0.50000
Total	N	20/50%	8/20%	12/30%
	Mean	1.3000	1.3750	1.1667
	Std. Deviation	0.47016	0.51755	0.38925

*N=Number of samples, *SSMO: Sudanese Standard Measurements Organization and *WHO: World Health Organization.

Table (5): The means statistics tested for compare differences across water sources of faecal *E. coli* and Total dissolved solids in drinking water samples, El-Obeid City.

TDS/SSMO - TDS/WHO		<i>E. coli</i> - House	<i>E. coli</i> - Animals cart	<i>E. coli</i> - Wells/Pump
Less than standard	N	12/30%	4/10%	1/2.5%
	Mean	1.4167	1.2500	1.0000
	Std. Deviation	0.51493	0.50000	0.0
Above standard	N	8/20%	8/20%	7/17.5%
	Mean	1.1250	1.1250	1.4286
	Std. Deviation	0.35355	0.35355	0.53452
Total	N	20/50%	12/30%	8/20%
	Mean	1.3000	1.1667	1.3750
	Std. Deviation	0.47016	0.38925	0.51755

4. DISCUSSION

The present study showed that about 72.5% of samples had taken from all sources contained fecal *E. coli*. The result is higher than a previous studies conducted in different areas; in El-Obeid city, Sudan; whereas found that about 57% of samples were polluted with *E. coli*.^[17] Additionally, a study carried out in similar area, it found that approximately 51.4% of the drinking water samples from all sources were polluted with *E. coli*.^[18] In Eastern zone, Tigrai, Ethiopia; it found that the leading water contaminant organisms were *Escherichia coli* 62.4%.^[19] In the Arida mountainous region, it found that 18% of drinking water samples contained pathogenic *E. coli*.^[20] Previous literature indicates that ideally, drinking water should not contain any microorganisms known to be pathogenic and should also be free from bacteria indicative of pollution with excreta.^[3] The following studies is in line with the current study, a similar study carried out in Lesotho, finding that total coliform and *E. coli* were present in 97% and 71% of the water samples, respectively.^[21] A study carried out in Jepara Regency, finding that 72.7% of samples were contaminated by *Escherichia coli*.^[22] A previous study carried out in El-Obeid city, found that all samples were contained *E. coli*, indicating poor water quality in the region. The proportion of contamination was highest in Hafrs, Gerabs, and household containers across seasons.^[23] The current result is lower than previous studies conducted in different areas, a study conducted in Nepal (Kathmandu Valley) and found widespread bacterial contamination of water sources, with 94% of sources having detectable total or fecal coliform.^[23] A study conducted in Northern Nigeria it's found that the results of microbiological analysis of the samples indicated that most of the wells were grossly contaminated with bacteria pathogens especially, *Escherichia coli* (100%) of drinking water samples.^[24]

The present study showed that (72%), (83%), and (62.5%) of samples had taken from houses, animal carts, and wells/pumps, respectively, contain *E. coli*. The results are higher than a previous study conducted in El-Obeid City (2017), which found (62%) of samples from houses contain *E. coli*, (52%) from tankers and gerbas contain *E. coli*, and (81%) from animal cart samples contain *E. coli*.^[17] Additionally, another study conducted in El-Obeid City (2017), finding that (59.3%), (27.3%), (72%), (44.9%),

and (52%) of samples from houses, tankers, animal carts, gerbas, and wells/pumps, respectively, contain *E. coli*.^[18]

CONCLUSION

Based on cluster analysis and comparisons with national (SSMO) and international (WHO) standards, this study evaluated the physicochemical and bacteriological quality of samples collected from households, animal carts (karo), and pump/wells in El-Obeid city. Although most parameters were within acceptable limits, the bacteriological quality was notably poor

Recommendations

urgent need for comprehensive, targeted interventions to improve water microbial quality. These interventions should include

- ✓ enhancing chlorination practices by ensuring proper chlorination at central collection or storage points.
- ✓ Maintaining adequate residual chlorine levels throughout the distribution system is crucial to prevent microbial contamination before delivering water to households.
- ✓ Control the physicochemical parameters of drinking water in water treatment plants, to ensure continuous supply of clean and safe drinking water to the consumers for public health protection
- ✓ Community-based water safety programs are crucial to raising awareness and mitigating contamination risks at the household level.

REFERENCES

1. Farah A. B. Abdallah, Ahmed M. Abu-Bakr. *Drinking water quality*. Khartoum state: University of Khartoum publishing house, 2017. <https://www.researchgate.net>
2. WHO. *Drinking water Parameter Cooperation Project* (Drinking Water Directive). Geneva: World Health Organization, 2017. <http://www.who.int>
3. Park, *Park Textbook of preventive and social Medicine*. 25th ed. Jabalpur: Banarsidas Bhanot, 2019.
4. Leonardo. B. et al. *Current Status of Drinking Water Quality in a Latin American Megalopolis*, 2022; 15(1): 3-4
5. Uloko, J.O. Assessment of Well Water Quality in Selected Part of Rafin Zurfi Area, Bauchi, North

- Eastern Nigeria. 11th ed. Conference Paper: University of Lagos Trade fair and Conference, 2016.
6. UNICEF. *Water, Sanitation and Hygiene*: United Nations Children's Fund (UNICEF) [Internet]. Geneva: Switzerland, 2014. Available from: <https://www.unicef.org/sudan>.
 7. World Health Organization. *Guidelines for drinking water quality*. 3th ed. World Health Organization, Geneva: WHO, 2008.
 8. Ibrahim A. M. M., Ahmed A. Y., Osman R. A., Noureldeen A. A., Ali I. H., Khuwaja G., Sayed S. F., Pawar H. A.. Microbiological Assessment and Treatment of Drinking Water Using Zinc Oxide Nanostructure in Khartoum, Sudan, *JCHR*. 2023; 13(6): 2598-2609.
 9. Sikder M., String G, Kamal Y., Farrington M., Rahman A. Sadiqur, and Lantagne D. Effectiveness of water chlorination programs along the emergency-transition post-emergency continuum: Evaluations of bucket, in-line, and piped water chlorination programs in Cox's Bazar. *Water Res.*, 2020; 178: 115854. DOI: 10.1016/j.watres.2020.115854.
 10. Mutasim A. Water Poverty and its Impact on Income Poverty and Health Status in Sudan: The Case of Gezira State. *IJAD*, 2017; 4(2): 99 - 100.
 11. James L. Joseph C, James. Bevan P. Greer and Jack. Bacteriological Disease Continuing Education Provisional Developing, CTLC., 2022; 431.
 12. World health organization. *Air quality guidelines*. 2th ed. Copenhagen, Denmark: WHO Officer for Europe, 2020.
 13. Directorate General of Health Affairs, Sheikan locality, North Kordofan State; El-Obied city, 2024.
 14. World Health Organization. *Guidelines for drinking - water quality- Surveillance and control of community supplies*. 2nd ed. Jabalpur: Banarsidas Bhanot, 1997.
 15. American Public Health Association (APHA). *Standard methods for the examination of water and waste water*. 21st ed. Washington DC, 2005.
 16. Sojobi. Assessment of Ground water quality and associated health risks: A case study of Ranchi city. *SD*, 2016; 5(2): 85-100.
 17. Tigaidi H, G. B. *Study of Drinking Water Quality in El-Obeid City North Kordofan State*. A thesis submitted in partial fulfillment of the requirements for M.Sc. in Public and Environmental Health. Al-Zaiem Al-Azhari University, 2017.
 18. Mohammed M. O. A., Ahmed M. E, Saeed O. K. and Tigaidi H, G. B. Assessment of Drinking Water Quality in El-Obeid City, North Kordofan State, Sudan. *IJSET*, 2017; 7(1): 2348-7968.
 19. Gebrewahd A, Adhanom G, Gebremichail G, Kahsay T, et al. Bacteriological quality and associated risk factors of drinking water in Eastern zone, Tigray, Ethiopia. *TDTMV*, 2019; 6(15): 1-7.
 20. Saeed M. Asif, Murtaza G., Ali S., Aziz H., et al. Assessment of Drinking Water Quality and Associated Socio-Economic Impacts in Arid Mountainous Regions. *S.*, 2022; 14: 12567.
 21. Gwimbi P. The Microbial Quality of Drinking Water in Manonyane community: Maseru District (Lesotho), Department of Environmental Health, National University of Lesotho. *AHS*, 2011; 11(3): 474-480.
 22. Rofiqi M. Fathin, Purwanta M., Lilik L. Djuari. Detection of Escherichia coli and Total Coliform in Refill Drinking Water at Jepara Regency. *IJRP.ORG.*, 2022; 109(1): 54-60
 23. Sarkar B, Mitchell E., Frisbie S., Grigg L., Adhikari S., and Byanju R. Maskey. Drinking Water Quality and Public Health in the Kathmandu Valley Nepal: Coliform Bacteria Chemical Contaminants, and Health Status of Consumers. *RAOA*, 2022; 3895859.
 24. Alkali A. U, Ali M and Bello M. Assessment on Effect of Anthropogenic Activities on Water Quality Parameters at Gundutse River in Kano Northern Nigeria. *SJ.*, 2022; 8(4): 124-126.